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**FALSAFA VA HAYOT
XALQARO JURNAL**

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**EXPLORING AC GRAYLING'S REALISTIC APPROACH TOWARDS
COMBATING SKEPTICISM IN CONTEMPORARY EPISTEMOLOGY**

Annotation: Grayling, one of the contemporary epistemologists is credited with developing realist approach to challenging skepticism and defending knowledge claims. The paper explores the theoretical basis of Grayling's approach and assesses its strength and weakness. Drawing the philosophy of philosophers like David Hume, John Locke, Grayling argues that skepticism is fundamentally misguided in its attempt to challenge the reliability of knowledge and instead proposes a more realistic approach which advocates for a moderate realism in which knowledge is seen to be a result of reliable processes, beliefs and experience, that is always provisional and subject to changes as new fact and circumstances arise. This allows for the possibility of knowledge without sacrificing the reality of uncertainty as well as practical and non dogmatic approach that is more consistent with complexities of the real world. The paper therefore affirms that Grayling's approaches is a proactive and insightful perspective in the sense that it allowing for a pragmatic and non-dogmatic approach that is more consistent with the complexities of our contemporary society.

Keywords: skepticism, knowledge, non-dogmatic, belief, reality, experience, epistemology, Grayling.

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**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ РЕАЛИСТИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА А. С.
ГРЕЙЛИНГА К ПРЕОДОЛЕНИЮ СКЕПТИЦИЗМА В
СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЭПИСТЕМОЛОГИИ**

Аннотация. Грейлинг, один из современных эпистемологов, заслужил признание за разработку реалистического подхода к преодолению

скептицизма и обоснованию познавательных притязаний. В статье рассматриваются теоретические основания подхода Грейлинга, а также оцениваются его сильные и слабые стороны. Опираясь на философию таких мыслителей, как Дэвид Юм и Джон Локк, Грейлинг утверждает, что скептицизм в своей основе ошибочен, поскольку ставит под сомнение надёжность знания, и вместо этого предлагает более реалистический подход. Этот подход опирается на умеренный реализм, в рамках которого знание рассматривается как результат надёжных процессов, убеждений и опыта, всегда носящих предварительный характер и подверженных изменениям по мере появления новых фактов и обстоятельств. Такой подход позволяет признавать возможность знания, не отказываясь от существующей неопределённости, и предлагает практическую, недогматическую позицию, более соответствующую сложности реального мира. Таким образом, статья утверждает, что подход Грейлинга является проактивным и проницательным взглядом, позволяющим применять прагматичный и недогматичный метод, согласующийся с реалиями современного общества.

Ключевые слова: скептицизм, знание, недогматизм, убеждение, реальность, опыт, эпистемология, Грейлинг.

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AC GRAYLINGNING ZAMONAVIY EPISTEMOLOGIYADA SKEPTITSIZMGA QARSHI KURASHISHDAGI REALIST YONDASHUVINI TADQIQ QILISH

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy epistemologlardan biri bo'lgan Grayling skeptitsizmga qarshi kurashish va bilim da'volarini himoya qilish bo'yicha realist yondashuvni ishlab chiqqani bilan tanilgan. Ushbu maqolada Graylingning yondashuvining nazariy asoslari o'rganiladi va uning kuchli hamda zaif jihatlari baholanadi. Deyvid Hume, Jon Lok kabi faylasuflarning falsafasiga tayangan holda Grayling skeptitsizmni bilim ishonchliligiga shubha bilan qaraydigan noto'g'ri yondashuv deb biladi va uning o'rniga moderat realizmga asoslangan, ya'ni bilim ishonchli jarayonlar, e'tiqod va tajribaning natijasi sifatida qaraladigan, doimo muvaqqat bo'lib, yangi faktlar va vaziyatlarga qarab o'zgarishga ochiq bo'lgan yondashuvni taklif qiladi. Bu yondashuv bilim imkoniyatini tan olgan holda, noaniqlik real holatini inkor etmaydi va amaliy, nodogmatik pozitsiyani ilgari suradi. Shu bois maqola Graylingning qarashlari zamonaviy jamiyatning murakkabliklariga mos ravishda pragmatik va nodogmatik yondashuvni ilgari suruvchi faol va chuqur fikrli nuqtai nazar ekanini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Skeptitsizm, bilim, nodogmatik, e'tiqod, haqiqat, tajriba, epistemologiya, Grayling.

INTRODUCTION

In the history of philosophy, the status and degree of our knowledge of the world, ourselves and others have been of great concerns to the philosophers, thus the questions such as; “what can be known”, what claims to knowledge can in principle be justified?, are sacrosanct to the philosophers. The answers to some of these questions may lead philosophers to either uphold or denounce certain knowledge if they feel that the criteria that have to be satisfied for such claims have not been met. The investigation and establishment of these general criteria that makes knowledge indubitable therefore becomes an important task of the philosophers because it helps to clarify the concept of knowledge. Among question that is usually asked towards these clarifications of our concept of knowledge is whether it is sense experience or reasoning that is primary in the acquisition of knowledge. In other words, are we to harmonize greater to knowledge that is acquired through sense experience or the one acquired through reason? This brand of question distinguishes rationalist and empiricist school of philosophy and eventually leads to the development of the skepticism principle. Among the contemporary philosophers who in one way or the other took a critical look on this subject matter is AC Graylings, he is one of those who have raised major issues and made hysterical efforts to resolving those fundamental issues. It is on his position on skepticism that the work critically examines some major issues raised in his work on skepticism and thereafter juxtaposes his realistic approach towards combating contemporary epistemological skepticism.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this paper employs a criticism approach to analyze and evaluate the interaction between Grayling approach to epistemic knowledge and ways of knowing. The paper explores the theoretical basis of Grayling’s approach and assesses its strength and weakness. Drawing the philosophy of philosophers like David Hume, John Locke, Grayling argues that skepticism is fundamentally misguided in its attempt to challenge the reliability of knowledge and instead proposes a more realistic approach which advocates for a moderate realism in which knowledge is seen to be a result of reliable processes, beliefs and experience, that is always provisional and subject to changes as new fact and circumstances arise. The methodology demonstrates that knowledge could be done by meeting the challenges shows that skeptical consideration would not in any way defeat our epistemic endeavour is commendable and to an extent, mind-provoking

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Epistemology as “theory of knowledge” is the branch of philosophy that tackles questions about the scope and source of human knowledge. The need for epistemological study comes from a desire to clarify and discover, if we can, what exactly defines “knowledge” as opposed to mere belief and how we can be sure whether or not our beliefs are justified. Thinkers have approached these questions in many different ways (and with varying degrees of success), but it seems clear

that skepticism has remained central to the project of epistemology throughout the history of philosophy. This is unsurprising, since the majority of epistemological theories (if not all of them) seem to have been developed as a response to skeptical arguments, either to defend or to oppose them.

Epistemology, according to Baldwin is the theory of the origin, nature and limits of knowledge. It is the branch of philosophy that investigates the process of human cognition and all problems associated with its acquisition and justification. It is the task of epistemology to refute or justify cognitive claims [Baldwin, 1960, p 45]. According to Ruch [Ruch, 1977, p. 55], ‘epistemology is the study of knowledge; more precisely it refers to objective and scientific knowledge (episteme) as opposed to opinion’. Ruch goes further to asserting that ‘epistemology is a study of a very special kind; it attempts to know knowledge, to have an insight into insights, to understand understanding and to frame a science about science. It is therefore a second order study, a meta-knowledge which is essentially reflective: the knower must look at himself in the process of his knowing and thinking activities [Ruch, 1977, p 528].

In the contemporary time, epistemology as defined by Hamlyn as no more than a desire to repudiate various versions of skepticism both the limited or mitigated and universal or unmitigated versions. From the definition of epistemology above, it is true that the idea of “knowledge” is of great importance to epistemological enterprise because the defining attribute of epistemology is the idea of knowledge or cognition [Hamlyn, 1970, p.45]. The question we need to ask at this juncture is: what is knowledge? And this will take us to the concept of knowledge.

The question of what can be known occupies a central place in philosophy since the time of Plato in ancient Greece. From the renaissance, epistemology has been keenly debated in the writings of philosophers such as Plato, Aristotle and Descartes. The question ‘what is knowledge’ is not only one of the most difficult questions to answer in philosophy on a daily basis, but also how we know what we claim to know and the justification of such claims to knowledge.

According to Bewaji [Bewaji, 2007, p. 88], there has hardly been any other concept that has been more enigmatic and a subject of greater controversy in epistemology than “knowledge”. He posits that it is interesting to investigate why it has been difficult, if not impossible, to arrive at an acceptable account of a concept that is a commonplace feature of our daily life. What is it to know that something is the case? What makes propositions expressing knowledge claims true or false? In short, what is “knowledge”? If these questions could be adequately answered, then other questions concerning what is knowable and sources and limits of knowledge could also be meaningfully and satisfactorily answered. However, the need to give an adequate definition of knowledge remains an existential imperative. It should be noted that the definitions that have featured prominently in epistemological treaties have been explicitly of propositional knowledge, such as, “S knows P” [Bewaji, 2007, p 30]

Knowledge according to Baldwin refers to:

1.The cognitive aspect of consciousness in general; to know means to perceive or apprehend or to understand.

2.Knowledge is also used in contrast to mere opinion sometimes called belief. In this application it signifies confidence based on adequate ground. There may be belief or subjective conviction without objective foundation.

4. Knowledge is further used for what is “known” as such. Thus, we speak of chemistry as a body of knowledge. Knowledge according to Baldwin is used as a synonym for cognition and also to specify cognition. That is the cognition that satisfies three conditions which are (1) Truth (2) Self-Satisfying and indubitability and (3) Logical impossible to falsify [Baldwin, 1960, p.56].

Since epistemology is interested in the discussion and analysis of the process interaction of the human mind (subject of knowledge) with the external world (object of knowledge), then it is the task of epistemology to understand the process of how humans became conscious of external objects. Mention should be made at this juncture that an epistemological analysis of consciousness differs from a psychological investigation of it because as Baldwin make us to understand while the latter is interested in the description of the process of cognition employing the empirical method, the former investigates cognitive materials in order to apprehend and prescribe the appropriate means of understanding external realities.

Skepticism has been defined generally as a philosophical concept questioning the possibility of knowledge object reality. In other words, according to Stumpt [Stumpt, 1977. p.67] skepticism maintains that the mind can overcome doubt for human reason is not only perverted and discussed but it is in itself fallacious, weak and instable. In view of this, skepticism has been a major issue in epistemology that requires hysterical efforts to authenticate our claims to knowledge.

The stereotype of a “skeptic” calls to mind one who constantly doubts the veracity of claims uttered around them, often to the great annoyance of the uttered. For example, when I claim to know that the tree outside my window is a lemon orange tree, the “doubter” might question whether I have identified the tree correctly perhaps it is a grape tree, or a lime. We might settle the doubt by referring to a mutually accepted authority on tree identification, examine the shape of the leaves and so on, to determine whether my lemon tree claim is true or not, when checked against a trusted source of knowledge on the topic. This sort of “skepticism” involves doubting the truth value of a particular empirical proposition that can be resolved by checking against another source of information. Skepticism involves a more radical kind of doubt that, by definition, cannot be resolved by any empirical “checking against” methods. A skeptical hypothesis of this kind would go further than merely doubting the accuracy of my tree-type identification; skepticism would call into question the claim that there is a tree outside my window at all. This distinction maps fairly well onto one basic difference between Ancient Skepticism and Modern Skepticism [James and Mark, 2014. p 67]. Whereas the Academic Skeptics and the Pyrrhonists suspended judgment to avoid holding any beliefs (which, after all, might be false), the Skepticism of modern

philosophy calls into doubt the possibility of claims to knowledge. Socrates engages with various interlocutors in a way similar to our aforementioned description of the “doubter” questioning the truth of their claims and scrutinizing their justifications. The hallmark of these dialogues is that they usually end in a mutual perplexity; the interlocutor begins with a confident claim to knowledge, Socrates helpfully points out the lack of evidence and logical fallacies, and both are left only with a negative kind of knowledge, i.e. an awareness of what is not the case. And, In Plato’s *Apology*, Socrates was portrayed as saying, “about myself I knew that I know nothing”. The skeptics of the Hellenistic Period carried on what they took to be the legacy of Socrates, arguing on both sides of a given philosophical argument to reach an informed state of intentional non-belief. By contrast, our modern skepticism takes the form of a systematized, globally applicable argument form that employs a specifically devised “skeptical hypothesis” to cast doubt on literally every conceivable claim to empirical knowledge. This sort of Skeptical Hypothesis posits an alternate possible world scenario which would give rise to a cognitive experience that is exactly similar to our commonsense “real world” and, therefore, be completely indistinguishable from it. The most famous examples of Skeptical Hypotheses come from René Descartes, who is credited as the source of what we now call “global skepticism”.

Epistemology is largely a response to skepticism. A subtext of virtually every theory of knowledge has been to show how knowledge is possible or, at the least, to avoid an account that delivers us unto the skeptic. A tortured epistemology has resulted from the conviction that a theory of knowledge must explain how knowledge is possible. If its consequences turn out not to be as terrible as we feared, and it yields an intuitive and useful account of knowledge, then skepticism itself becomes an attractive option in epistemology. In any case, it is unlikely that skepticism should have proved so durable if it reveals nothing of importance about knowledge; and we can hardly expect to learn what something teaches so long as we doggedly resist it. Stone for that reason asserts that to learn what it teaches, therefore, I propose to capitulate to skepticism [Stone, 1984. p. 45]

Once epistemology is relieved of the task of rescuing knowledge from skepticism, it becomes relatively easy to give an account of knowledge: knowledge is indubitable certainty, as Descartes believed. That is, S knows that p if and only if S believes p truly and, given S's warrant, rational doubt that p is impossible. Our theory of knowledge will be internalistic, so that knowledge, if we have it, would be a rational antidote to doubt and wonder, one of the chief reasons we have always want knowledge. This theory doesn't entail we know nothing, however, but only that we know very little. Perhaps we know the sort of things Descartes thought we knew. My attentive belief that there is a thought now is indubitable, for instance; for it must be true if I doubt it. And when I know there is a thought now, this makes it indubitable that something exists if only the thought. Nonetheless, to know “p”, I must be able to rule out every conceivable mistake. In the case of contingent beliefs, this requires that E (the evidence on the basis of which I believe p) entails the non actuality of every possible world in which not-p. Otherwise, for

all I know, this is one of those worlds; so, for all I know, p is false. This argument is intuitive and forceful, and, once we no longer need to resist the skeptic, we have no reason not to accept it.

However, Skepticism is often rejected on the ground that it denies the truth of all our ordinary knowledge claims. Keith writes: "The bold skeptic thus implicates us in systematic and widespread falsehood in our use, in speech and in thought, of our very common word "knows" [Keith, 1992. p 35]. Worse, the skeptic denies them on account of ridiculous considerations. When I say 'I know there are three chairs at the table, I've counted them twice,' it is absurd to object: 'How do you know you're not a brain in a storage bin? It is worth emphasizing, therefore, that it is not a consequence of an enlightened skepticism that such utterances are false, but only those they make, not claims to knowledge, but a closely related, weaker sort of statement. The skeptic can explain the utility of the idea of knowledge in our ordinary practices, even though we never have knowledge, Knowledge functions there as an idealization.

Skepticism as an Epistemic Challenge

The idea of finding unshakable foundation for knowledge is against skepticism, which claims that we cannot be certain about our epistemic claims. Skepticism as an idea connotes the critical spirit: the tendency of not being easily satisfied with simple or superficial evidence and striving to accept only incorrigible beliefs that are absolutely certain [Owolabi, 2000. p 67]. It is usually not easy to describe the features of skepticism since there are diverse and different reasons and objectives that prompt skeptical denial of certainty and objectivity of our epistemic claims. One sure thing however is that the aim of skepticism is to establish the need to properly scrutinize our epistemic claims to ensure that our epistemic claims are free from doubt. To this end, skepticism has been the force propelling the epistemological enterprise. According Ayer [Ayer, 1956. p.33] , these skeptical challenges supply the main subject matter for what is called theory of knowledge; and different philosophical standpoints are characterized by the acceptance or denial of different stages of the skeptic's argument. We may therefore describe skepticism as the epistemological doctrine that challenges our cognitive claims by providing arguments and reasons why those cognitive claims should be doubted.

There are variations in the arguments of the skeptics; these variations include:

(1) The doubt of epistemic claims based on the source of knowledge. Most of our knowledge claims come from the sense experience and the senses have been shown to be deceitful and cannot be reliable guide to knowledge of the future.

(2) The doubt directed at theoretical knowledge as some skeptics argue that we can easily make mistakes in our deductive and mathematical inferences. This only shows we cannot be sure of the inferences we make from mathematical axioms.

(3) The doubts that arise from the similarity between actual reality and states of dream. Since it is always difficult to differentiate between these two, some

skeptics argue that it is only sensible to regard our experiences as a dream from which we can wake up one day. Thus, we should not take actual experiences as absolutely certain.

(4) The doubts prompted by the Cartesian “evil genius” hypothesis. According to Descartes, it is possible for us to be constantly deceived by an “evil genius.” If this is the case, it would mean that all our knowledge is deceitful and unreliable [Owolabi, 2000. p 89].

Based on these variations in skeptical arguments, Slote [Slote, 1970] summarizes the essential thesis of skepticism as; “by skepticism about X (where X could mean any empirical claim) I shall mean or view that some hypothesis about X is no less reasonable than its deniable, which means that there is no more reason to believe that X exists than that X does not exist and that it is consequently unreasonable to believe that X exists.

Inherent in this understanding of Slote is the idea that skepticism is oriented towards the belief that our epistemic claims are not justifiable as a result of some natural problems about our interaction with the external world. This understanding points at the very heart of the problem of certitude and skepticism in traditional Western epistemology, namely, the idea that until the knowing subject accurately represents the known object as it is in the eternal world, we cannot talk about knowledge. Thus, rational certainty, which guarantees knowledge, is understood within the parameters of accuracy of representation by the knowing subject.

We can distinguish between a numbers of different varieties of skepticism. First, one might be a skeptic only with regard to certain domains, such as mathematics, morality, or the external world (this is the most well-known variety of skepticism). Such a skeptic is a local skeptic, as contrasted with a global skeptic, who maintains that we cannot know anything at all. Also, since knowledge requires that our beliefs be both true and justified, a skeptic might maintain that none of our beliefs are true or that none of them are justified (the latter is much more common than the former).

Grayling’s idea of skepticism begins by observing that epistemology as a branch in philosophy attempts to answer the question of what knowledge is, and what are the best as well as the most secure ways of acquiring knowledge. In traditional debate on the matter, knowledge is standardly defined as “justified true belief”(JTB), at least, it seems that to know something, one ought to believe it, one’s belief must be satisfactory in the light of some standard because one could not be said to know something if one had, say arbitrarily or, haphazardly decided to believe [Lirde, 1998. p 9]. Each of the three parts of the definition seems to express a necessary condition for knowledge that the claim is taken together, the conditions is sufficient for knowledge. However, one fundamental question is how we define knowledge and another is about how we get knowledge. The criterion for rationalists is mathematics and logic, where necessary truth are reached by rational deductions or inference, while model for the empiricist is of the natural sciences where “observation and experimentation” are the main vehicle of inquiring. Grayling [Grayling, 2008. p 22] therefore opines that the demonstration

of the possibility of knowledge can be done by meeting the challenges to show skeptical considerations do not after all define our best epistemic endeavours.

In his view, Grayling describes skeptic as one who at least; unless he is shown satisfactory reason why he should do otherwise, doubt some propositions, belief or theory. Grayling opines that skeptical attitude is healthy when it aims upon our credence by whoever they are being made. He therefore submits that it is impossible for one to be skeptical about everything, giving instance of a society which cannot as a matter of fact, function unless some individual are seen to be honest and most information reliable most of the time. But that there are instances where it is appropriate even when necessary for one to be skeptical, where the responsibility course is to query a given claim and to assess the case offered in support. He maintained that in philosophy, the use and study of skepticism or skeptical arguments belongs to epistemology and in one sense might be said to define it. Implicit in this characterization are two important claims by Grayling which are namely:

That skepticism is best understood as a challenge, not as an analogical claim that we do or can know nothing and that the best way to respond to skepticism is not by attempting to prove false on an argument basis, but by showing how we know. Upon this is the Grayling's main argument.

Grayling explained that skeptical argument explore certain contingent psychological facts concerning the means we get, test, remember and reason about our beliefs. Given that knowledge consists in belief which is time and in a way to be defined well justified, any problem which infects the acquisition and engagement of beliefs about a particular subject-matter endangers our claims to knowledge in respect of that subject- matter [Grayling, 2008, p.45]

The psychological facts in question are those relating to nature of perception, the normal human vulnerability to error and the existence of state of mind such as dreaming and delusion which could be subjectively indistinguishable from those we take to be appropriate for acquiring knowledge. Therefore the skeptic purpose is to show that there are important questions that need answers concerning the level of confidence we are supposed to repose in our standard ways of getting knowledge. The rationalist does not need to deny that empirical awareness is not a vital adjunct of our rational faculties, nor the empiricist that reason is an essential adjunct of empirical investigation both will however, hold that the primary, chief or final means to knowledge is respectively one or the other. The main fact is that skepticism is a problem for both rationalist and empiricism. Both have problem, a result of the possibilities of error and delusion, which poses a challenge, more to empiricist because of perception and perceptual consciousness.

The arguments arising from errors emanates from the fact that we are fallible and sometimes make mistakes. If we claim for instance to known proposition say R, we ought to be able to exclude the possibility that simultaneously knowing R. But since we do not frequently realize as we commit error, we are not justified in making such a claim. The same is applicable to delusion, illusion or hallucination. More often than not, one does not know when one is in this situation and assumes

oneself to be having veridical experience. Although the person assumes he is in this state, which gives itself to his being justified in claiming to know a given R he is not so. In this case the person does not know what he claims to know. So in order for anyone to claim knowledge of some R, one ought to exclude the possibility that one is the subject of such a situation

The synopsis of above argument is the possibility of error, delusion or dreaming acts such as a vanquisher to knowledge-claims for example if one knows R, then nothing is acting to subvert one's entitlement to know it. But one can seem to oneself fully entitled to claim to know some R and obviously not be as such, as the foregoing consideration show. In view of this our claim to knowledge are in need of better ground than we standardly take ourselves to have. We ought to find a way of defeating the defeaters.

This problem arises from the limitation of sensory experience for instance, the reflection of light from the surface of the objects in the physical environment which passes into the eyes, where it irritates the cells of the retina in such a way that the impulses are triggered in the optic nerves. The nerves carry the impulse to the part of the cerebral cortex, which process visual data where they stimulate certain kind of brain activity. Consequently, coloured pictures are raised in the consciousness of the subject of these events representing the world outside his head. This reoccurs in the other sensory pathways of hearing, smelling and touch. But the skeptic can use criterion to make another application of the defeater argument.

Grayling submitted that skeptical arguments are not best dealt with by attempt at direct refutation on one by one basis. Two ways skepticism might employ in epistemology in his view are:

I. An agnological result- that is, one which positively affirms that we are ignorant about some subject matter, but when they ask us to justify our claims to knowledge. A challenge to justify is not a claim or a theory and cannot be refuted. it can only be accepted or ignored. Since the skeptic gives reason why justification is needed, the response might be to inspect those reasons to see whether the challenge needs response (Grayling 2008). This for him, is obviously one good response to skepticism where the reasons are cogent, the next good response is to try to meet the challenge pose as such.

II. The other is that the bulk range of skeptical argument taken together has maieutic status. Maieutic literally connotes midwifery that is the practice of helping childbirth. Anything that has this status is something that would help something else into being.

To argue that skeptic considerations are maieutic means that they together usher into light what is required for a satisfactory theory of knowledge. If one could debunk or show to be grounded, one or another particular skeptical argument, others would be left at a place yet asking that we provide a possible account of knowledge.

Albert Ryles' attempt at refuting the argument form error by a polar concept argument can illustrate the above points. In his arguments, there cannot be

counterfeit coins without genuine ones as one cannot talk about short men without talking about tall men. In this line of argument, the polar concept of error is right. So if we understand that we can be in error sometimes, we will invariably understand we can sometimes be right. This argument is aimed at refuting the claim that we can always be in error [Bittle, 1936, p 56]. But what he is saying is that the skeptic does not claim this rather asking how, given that we sometimes make mistakes, we can rule off the possibility of being in error on any given occasion of judgment maybe, at the present time. For Ryle also, the skeptic does need to concede to the more general claim. Ryle makes namely that for any conceptual polarity, both poles must be understood and more to understand a concept is to know how to apply it and for it to be applicable is for it actually to be applied [Bittle, 1936, p 89]. This is question begging enough but so is the claim about conceptual polarities denoted expressions perfect-imperfection, moral-immoral, finite- infinite where it is by no means clear that the more exotic poles apply to anything or even that we really understand them.

What seems to be saying is that these thoughts appear in such a way that skeptical arguments even if singly they seem implausible, joint call for an earnest reply which is what in big measure epistemology quest to offer. But yet there are the issues of the distinction to be understood. Descartes aims are to discover a thing he can sure serves a ground for certainty. He needs to exclude anything allowing any way the least faint of doubt, nevertheless absurd that doubt for only then will reveal what is lovely and indubitable be unveiled. Citing the fact that one can easily be misled by one's perception, this does not hold enough water in the sense that we can make perceptual mistakes and yet claim to know something. Grayling submits that Descartes successors are not impressed by the skeptical argument. The diagnosis of the problem was accepted and not the cure. Thus, for tradition of epistemological thinking after his time, these and allied skeptical arguments were not mere methodological devices but problems requiring solution. Hence the distinction he draws between methodological and problematical skepticism, Grayling makes two submissions about `Descartes position which are

I.Certainty having been a psychological situation one can find oneself independent of whether one is right or wrong. The falsity of a belief is no bar to one's feeling certain that it is true. Descartes aim was to devise a way of recognizing our beliefs that are true

II.Secondly he believes that the role of epistemology is to avail us with a way of knowing [Grayling, 2008, p.78]

Responding to the Skeptic view, Grayling is of the opinion that the general result of skeptical challenge points out that we suffer an epistemic plight, our possession of best possible evidence for believing some say P and still not right in other words. It means that skepticism goes down to the observation that "there is nothing contradictory our best grounds for a given belief P with the falsity of P are not a contradiction. He submits that skepticism represented in this way, can informatively be seen as the opening of a gap between the evidence any putative knower has for the knowledge claims he makes on one hand and those claims

themselves on the other hand. Replies to skepticism severally take the form of efforts either to bridge the gap or to close it

Also, skepticism challenges us to justify our belief in the unperceived continued existence of objects for how do we know that a thing remains in existence when we do not perceive them. Using transcendental argument of Kant, one can reply that because we take ourselves to occupy one single unified world of spatio-temporary where objects have to exist unperceived in order to make the realm as one and unified, a belief in their unperceived continued existence in a condition of our thinking about the world and our experience of it in this way. So the belief the skeptic challenge us to justify is also thereby justified.

Idealism and phenomenism according to Grayling has been another way of refuting skepticism saying there is no gap of the sort the skeptic alleges. Thus Berkeley submits that skepticism emanates from assuming that beyond or behind our sensory experience there is a material world. Material implying made of matter and is assumed to be technical philosophical term to denote empirical undetectable substance believed to Berkeley's predecessors to underlie the sensory detectable qualities of things like shapes and colours

The point that is noted is that Berkeley tried to refute skepticism by not accepting that there exist a gap between experience and reality on the basis that experience and reality have no difference. The phenomenist with one vital difference argued otherwise. Their opinion is in short that all our belief about the world are derived from what appears to us in experience thus appearance and phenomena are taken to mean the same thing

Grayling fundamentally believes that some epistemologist do not try to refute skepticism since they think it is either true or irrefutable. In other words, skepticism is the inevitable result of attempts to think about knowledge, so we must accept either that we only ever going to have to imperfectly justified beliefs or that we have to recognize that what skepticism implies, despite being irrefutable, is not a practical option and therefore we have to live as most people do namely by simply ignoring it.

However, all arguments inference drawn from various philosophers above boils down to the fact that A.C Grayling has raised some major issues in epistemology and philosophy in general

In the brief exposition more emphasis is laid on the fact that skepticism defines the central problem in epistemology which is the need to show how knowledge is made possible. This could be done by meeting the challenges to show that skeptical consideration do not after all defeat our best epistemic endeavours. The two implications here are that skepticism is best understood as a challenge, not as an agnological claims that we do or can know nothing and secondly, that the best way to respond to skepticism is not by attempting to refute it on an argument by argument basis but by showing how we know.

Grayling opines that the demonstration of knowledge could be done by meeting the challenges shows that skeptical consideration would not in any way defeat our epistemic endeavour is commendable and to an extent, mind-provoking.

i.e skepticism to be understood as a challenge, not as an agnological claim that we do or can know nothing can provides a little watering ground for the two schools of thought viz- rationalism and empiricism. This is because the challenges ought to be applicable to either means or tools of knowledge acquisition in a way of their periodical examination and re-examination as to update our knowledge of the world and ourselves

Furthermore, Grayling stands that the best way to respond to skepticism is not argument by argument basis but to show how we know call for explanation of what he means by argument. Does he means just argument for the sake of arguing or otherwise? Can epistemological claims be debunked and a better option provided, if it is not by argument?. However, one can still argue that he means those important questions that need answers pertaining the level confidence we are to repose in our standard ways of acquiring knowledge. But then, who and what determine the acceptable level of confidence to be reposed in our standard ways of getting knowledge?

Besides, Grayling's position that a challenge to justify is neither a claim nor a theory is also commendable to a reasonable extent, but that it cannot be refuted and that it could be accepted or ignored might be taken with a pinch of salt by many philosophers. He maintains further that since the skeptics gives reason why justification is needed, the response might be to inspect those reasons to see whether the challenges need where they are cogent, the next response is to try to meet the challenges thereby posed.

From the above position, one can deduce elements of subjectivism in respect of what to respond to, and what not to and then does not augur well for the growth of knowledge regarded as indubitable. It becomes a case of where every individual is to be his own judge of what should constitute a good challenge. What of intentions that are not easily predictable in whatever one does?

Grayling's reason that range of skeptical argument taken together a maieutic means that will together user into what is needed for a satisfactory theory of knowledge. Maieutic meaning helping childbirth or in other words, anything that has the status of helping something into being. This is realistic and acceptable in the sense that in epistemic endeavours from inception have been often provoked by one form of skepticism or the other. Once a claim to knowledge has been faulted, an alternative and amendment is normally provided by the skeptic or the person that has provided such a claim. Put in the other way round, skepticism has been a necessary philosophical tool for the re-examination and modification of any existing claims to knowledge or any true justified knowledge itself.

Descartes maintains that The theory of knowledge is among other things , a set of defense work against skepticism of possibility of knowledge. This must have informed Grayling's position that diagnose of the problem has been accepted in epistemology rather than the cure by Descartes successors. However, Grayling might be said to open another meaningful way of discussion in epistemology in terms of combating skepticism in contemporary time, but in as much as his

suggested approach cannot be dismissed with a wave of hand they are not prone to some faults that have been identified.

One should think that the problem of both rationalist and empiricist, skeptics is being a bit dogmatic in adopting their stands respectively that only the tool each uses is reliable. For instance, Rene Descartes proposes to hold in doubt anything that could not be seen in the light of reason to be certain and indubitable (Hamlyn 1972), owing to his belief that all true knowledge comes through reason which has innate ideas of all realities, the analysis of these innate ideas is adequate for the discovery of all truths, the other hand, the empiricist believe that valid knowledge is at one point or the other given by perception. It is free from possibility of error since error has no place in what is given; error they opine is as a result of imagination or frailty of human judgment.

Summarizing Kant's phenomenism, Rich says:

I cannot doubt the subjective experience which I have, neither can I transcend the subjective world in order to reach a reality beyond the mind, I never know the world as it is in itself [Ruch, 1977, s.528]

The above is an attack on metaphysics, which Kant regards as an illusion. The above position is based on assumption that knowledge implies certainty and certainty is itself unattainable. This is problematic in the sense that if the skeptic maintains that everything is doubtful, it follows by this very argument that the idea that everything is doubtful is itself doubtful.

Again, if there is no other thing the skeptics can admit that we know with certainty, they should at least be convinced that the act of doubt is itself a form of certainty, for it is a fact that anyone who engages in doubt knows certainty that he or she doubts something and no one can be in error if she does not exist. St Augustine and Descartes subscribe to this view; one certainty is the certainty that exist. Whatever else one can have doubt, he cannot doubt that Descartes ought to have written more correctly, *dubito ergo sum* meaning "I doubt therefore I am" instead of *cogito ergo sum*, "I think therefore I am" [Griffiths, 1967, p 1]. That if the mind can then know this one truth with certainty. It follows that mind is naturally endowed with the ability to know and if this is acceptable, it cannot always and necessarily be in error. So if both schools of thought could shift their ground from absolute doubt and superiority of tools to acquisition of knowledge to reconstruction and reconciliatory ways of reaching all kinds of knowledge, will be reduced. After all, doubt is not a necessary aspect of cognition and therefore should not be held as such. But if absolute doubt is impossible, it follows that wholesale skepticism is also impossible but instantiations of skepticism

CONCLUSION

It seems from all indication that the empiricist skeptics think that by not accepting what is not given in sense experience like metaphysics, science can develop the more. If however, metaphysics and science are seen as competing for

explanation of man and all that this world is , such a competition is a healthy one since one is inadequate. Though the contemporary world is not in favour of metaphysics according to Grayling partly because of the extension scientific knowledge and the accompanying assumption that science alone can provide knowledge. But disagree with this notion. It also seems metaphysics that uses reasons as tools in dubitable knowledge is guilty of not accepting and acknowledging the conclusion of science. Based on this, they become unnecessarily dogmatic in both their belief and practice. They often see metaphysics as a completing field to science in explanation of the world, and at the same time, take it as providing a sort of super scientific knowledge.

Nevertheless, science explains much, but still cannot explain all there is to know. For instance, science cannot explain the beginning and the end of man. The growth of knowledge in contemporary time if the empiricist recognize the fundamental functions of reason in explaining man's abstract world bearing in mind that science has its own limit while the rationalists accept scientific explanations with an open mind, so that people like A.C Grayling can now talk about discovery of knowledge and not burying their heads to findings ways to combat skepticism in contemporary epistemology

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